

Using Knowledge Graphs for Navigating Data Assets

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Talk Outline

- Semantic layers
- Building atop relational knowledge graph management systems
 - Ontology modeling
 - Exploring the ontology using KGs: semantic search
 - Semantic layer implementation: weaving data into the ontology
- Problem: verifying the trustworthiness of a semantic layer
- Solution: drill-down capability from conceptual to physical level
- Live demo

Semantic Layer

- Presents a unified *view* of the data to the user
- Allows the user to express search queries in terms of business concepts and relationships
- Allows extensibility of the views

Approaches to Semantic Modeling

- SQL-first proposals
 - [DBT \(announcement\)](#) - SQL based approach
 - [Malloy \(link\)](#) - Google/Looker proposal to succeed LookML that maps to SQL
- Semantic Data Catalogs and Data Fabrics
 - Knowledge graph-based [catalogs](#) and [fabrics](#)
- Industry proposals
 - [Legend](#) by Goldman Sachs - UML + OCL inspired approach. Runs on SQL
 - [Morphir](#) by Morgan Stanley ([intro video](#)) - Functional programming based approach. Runs on Spark
- Standards body Proposals:
 - [Semantic Web](#) - W3C standard. SPARQL, RDF, [OWL](#), [SHACL](#)
 - [SBVR](#) - OMG standard for “Semantics of Business Vocabulary and Rules”

RelationalAI powers all approaches

Conceptual Modeling using Object Role Modeling (ORM)

- Mature notation for representing ontologies and methodology for eliciting concepts, relationships, rules, and constraints
- Well supported by tools like the Natural ORM Architect (NORMA)
- Strong verbalization of models supports conceptual queries
- Adopted in industry

T. Halpin and T. Morgan, *Information Modeling and Relational Databases*, Elsevier, 2008.

Example: Ontology Modeling

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Table Details Columns [Data Preview](#) Copy History

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	LINE_ITEM_ID	AMOUNT	BILL_ID	COVERED_PRODUCT_CODE
1	90,001	12.99	10,001	30001
2	90,002	10	10,001	30002
3	90,003	5.99	10,002	30003
4	90,004	12.99	10,002	30001

Example: Ontology Modeling

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Semantic Search

- Tool to explore the ontology of the business domain
 - Provides vocabulary for search queries
- Output of the search: list of precise names of concepts and relationships of interest
 - Helps with framing queries using business concepts and relationships rather than using names of tables and columns in the physical layer

Example: Semantic Search

Query string:

```
def insert:input_concept_name = {  }  
def insert:input_relationship_name = {  }
```

Output:

Example: Semantic Search

Query string:

```
def insert:input_concept_name = {"Bill"}  
def insert:input_relationship_name = { }
```

Output:

Example: Semantic Search

Query string:

```
def insert:input_concept_name = {"Bill"}  
def insert:input_relationship_name = {"LineItemIsPartOfBill"}
```

Output:

Semantic Search

- Details are discussed in our MODELS'22 paper [1]
- Preprint:

[1] Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems: Companion Proceedings, October 2022 Pages 81–82, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3550356.3559576>

ORM Ontologies with Executable Derivation Rules to Support Semantic Search in Large-Scale Data Applications

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ABSTRACT

A semantic layer maps complex enterprise data into an ontology with abstract business concepts that are well-known to business users. Chief data officers invest significant effort to create and update these ontologies, while data scientists do feature engineering by combining already existing concepts and features of the domain. However, it is a significant challenge to catalogue and maintain the numerous features pertaining to an ontology, which leads to duplicated features and unnecessary complexity. In this work, we propose to combine ontologies captured using the Object-Role Modeling notation with derivation rules defined in a datalog-like language called Rel, which allows the creation of a semantic layer with feature search capability. Our prototype framework uses the RAI Knowledge Graph Management System, which provides automated and incremental derivation rule evaluation.

ACM Reference Format:

Márton Búr and Kurt Stirewalt. 2022. ORM Ontologies with Executable Derivation Rules to Support Semantic Search in Large-Scale Data Applications. In *ACM/IEEE 25th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS '22 Companion)*, October 27–28, 2022, Montréal, QC, Canada. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3550356.3559576>

1 INTRODUCTION

Data scientists perform *feature engineering* to distill a set of features that can be analyzed to predict some outcome of interest. Feature engineering at enterprise scale is expensive because:

- (1) Enterprise data are rarely designed to be accessible by those with domain knowledge and a business problem to solve but little or no design knowledge of the applications that create and use the data; and
- (2) The number of features can grow into the tens of thousands, making the cataloging and maintenance of the feature set a significant software engineering challenge.

Recently, chief data officers have started building *semantic layers* to address the first problem. Semantic layers weave low-level enterprise data into a common ontology that is consumable by those with knowledge of the domain.

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Figure 1: Example ontology and a feature (ORM)

We believe the second problem can be made tractable by means of *semantic search* if data scientists engineer features on top of a semantic layer. A feature is a relationship computed over concepts from the ontology using a recipe that ultimately derives from relationships that are declared in the ontology. A consumer should be able to search for any feature by naming the concept(s) that it ranges over and one or more of the relationships (called *ingredients*) of its recipe. In fact, even if a consumer does not know all of a recipe's ingredients, they can often name at least some, which often suffices to narrow the search to a small enough set of matching features. If the language used to declare ontologies and features provides a means for declaring derived relationships – and if those recipes can be analyzed formally – then data scientists can search for features in large feature sets using concepts and relationships from the ontology. However, up to our best knowledge, there is no ontology modeling language providing these capabilities.

This work uses ontologies declared in the Object Role Modeling notation (ORM) [4] supplemented with feature definitions written in a datalog-like language called Rel to help data scientists search for and reason about feature sets in terms of the business domain. Our solution is novel because we provide a framework that (1) on the meta-level allows loading the ontology into a knowledge graph and creating a semantic layer that provides search functionality across all features, and (2) supplements ORM with executable derivation rules built from the concepts and features of the ontology.

2 REPRESENTING ONTOLOGIES & FEATURES

We use the Object Role Modeling (ORM) notation designed for conceptual modeling to declare an ontology and any features that are derived from the semantic layer that populates the ontology. The first row of Figure 1 depicts the ontology of a fictional enterprise that sends out bills to its customers. ORM depicts concepts as rounded rectangles and relationships as one or more adjacent rectangles (called *roles*) that are linked to the concept that plays the role in the relationship. This ontology declares four concepts – Customer, Bill, BillLineItem, and UsageAmount – and three relationships – “Bill is billed to Customer”, “BillLineItem covers UsageAmount”, and “BillLineItem belongs to Bill”.

Enterprise-Wide Semantic Layers

Managing and accessing large scale enterprise data stored in data silos is a huge challenge in the industry

- Several teams using several different methods to access and work with the data
- Synchronization, change propagation, and duplication is problematic

The view of the data that a semantic layer provides promises to solve this problem

- Source data live in the modern data stack
- A knowledge-graph management system incrementally maintains the views and supports queries over the ontology

Weaving source data into ontology

- Declarative rules that are executable
 - Rule definitions include data lineage information, which follows the *model is the code* principle
- Rules follow a small number of weaving patterns
 - Tools using reflection can transitively explore how data is woven into the layer

Example: Weaving source data into ontology

```
value type Amount = Decimal
def LineItem(li) { line_item:charges(li, _) }
module line_item
  ...
  def charges(li, amt) {
    li = ^LineItem[^LineItemId[SALES:LINE_ITEM_ID[row]] and
    amt = ^Amount[SALES:AMOUNT[row]]
    from row
  }
  ...
end
...
```


Example: Weaving source data into ontology

```
value type Amount ← Decimal
def LineItem(li) { line_item:charges(li, _) }
module line_item
...
def charges(li, amt) {
  li = ^LineItem[^LineItemId[SALES:LINE_ITEM_ID[row]] and
  amt = ^Amount[SALES:AMOUNT[row]]
  from row
}
...
end
...
```


Source columns

Relationship

Concepts

Trusting the Weaving Rules

Problem: data weaving rules might contain errors

Two key kinds of queries are needed to address this problem:

- **Semantic search:** users can navigate and explore the ontology
- **Drill-down:** concepts/relationships in the ontology are mapped to names in the physical layer which provides data lineage

Added value:

- **Rapid exploration of the domain**
- **Layer trustworthiness**

Demo

Summary

- Relational knowledge graphs by nature are well suited for implementing semantic layers
- Semantic search makes it possible to rapidly find concepts/relationships of interest
- The ability to link conceptual models to data sources allows data consumers to check the veracity of the semantic layer

